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The four basic fields of nature

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Abstract

BACKGROUND:

The pursuit of a Unified Field Theory (UFT) has captivated the scientific community for decades, driven by the quest to unify the fundamental forces of nature into a single, elegant framework.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This article delves into the mathematical possibilities, challenges, and other aspects in the development of UFT.

RESULTS:

Drawing inspiration from Einstein's pioneering work in General Relativity, the study examines new mathematical approaches to UFT. Through an analysis of collaboration, feedback, and the legacy left by Einstein's endeavors, this article sheds important mathematical light on the intricate nature of UFT, the mathematical complexities of unifying diverse forces, and the enduring impact of UFT on theoretical physics.

CONCLUSION:

As modern physics continues to seek a comprehensive description of the universe, this article provides deep and new mathematical insights into the journey toward a unified understanding of nature's fundamental forces.

Keywords:

Fields; Basic fields of nature, Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation; Unified field theory

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1. Introduction

Our endeavors to elicit the objective reality, even the profoundest mysteries, are not always straightforward or immediately linked to success. Rather, they necessitate perpetual attempts to approach a quandary and discover a novel approach, in order to reconsider that which has been overlooked or misjudged. This challenge proves notably formidable, particularly when endeavouring to fully geometricize Einstein's field equations. As is well known, the Einstein field equations (Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1917, 1935; Einstein and Sitter, 1932) describe the relationship between the presence of matter, represented by the stress-energy tensor $\left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu}\right)$, in a given region of space-time and the curvature in that region by the equation

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (1)$$

$$\equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$$

(Einstein, 1916, 1917)

where $R_{\mu\nu}$ is the Ricci tensor (Ricci-Curbastro and Levi-Civita, 1900) of 'Einstein's general theory of relativity' (Einstein, 1916), R is the Ricci scalar, the trace of the Ricci curvature tensor with respect to the metric and equally the simplest curvature invariant of a Riemannian manifold, Λ is the Einstein's cosmological (Barukčić, 2015a; Einstein, 1917) constant, $\underline{\Lambda}$ is the "anti cosmological constant" (Barukčić, 2015a), $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor of Einstein's general theory of relativity, $G_{\mu\nu}$ is Einstein's curvature tensor, $\underline{G}_{\mu\nu}$ is the "anti tensor" (Barukčić, 2016b) of Einstein's curvature tensor, $E_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of energy, T is Laue's (see also Einstein and Grossmann, 1913; Laue, 1912; von Laue, 1911) scalar, $\underline{E}_{\mu\nu}$ is the tensor of non-energy, the anti-tensor of the stress-energy tensor of energy, $a_{\mu\nu}$, $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$ denote the four basic fields of nature were $a_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter, $b_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, c is the speed of the light in vacuum, G is Newton's gravitational "constant" (Barukčić, 2015a,b, 2016a,b), π is Archimedes constant pi, D is space-time dimension. The n-th index D dimensional Einstein's field equations have been derived as

$$\left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu\dots}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu\dots}\right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu\dots}) \equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu\dots} \quad (2)$$

(Barukčić, 2020a,b)

One of the strengths of this more generalized version of the Einstein's gravitational field equations

with additional n-th indices in lower and in higher dimensions than 4 while completely geometrized is their simplicity and predictive power. Even if similar equations are often considered in the context of theories beyond Einstein's original general relativity, such as in string theory or higher-dimensional gravity theories, the extended n-th index D dimensional Einstein's gravitational field equations attempt to unify different fundamental forces, such as gravity and electromagnetism, within a single framework. This should lead to a more comprehensive understanding of the fundamental forces of the nature. Nonetheless, even if the extended n-th index D dimensional Einstein's field equations are a fascinating area of theoretical physics, they might come with both advantages and challenges. These equations hold the potential to provide deeper insights into the fundamental properties of nature but also might introduce complexities and difficulties in their application and verification. In this context, the Ricci tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ has been decomposed into the four fundamental fields of nature, denoted as $a_{\mu\nu}$, $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$ without contradiction as

$$a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} \equiv R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \quad (3)$$

where D is the space-time dimension, tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ represents the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter, $b_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, and so forth. This logic holds coherently and applies irrespective of the specific nature and configuration of the fundamental fields of nature denoted by $a_{\mu\nu}$, $b_{\mu\nu}$, $c_{\mu\nu}$ and $d_{\mu\nu}$. As compellingly demonstrated already, there are indeed conditions where the field $c_{\mu\nu}$ assumes the value of

$$c_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \quad (4)$$

However, it must be queried at this point, is this always and under all conceivable circumstances true? The subsequent illustration (see table 1) is intended to provide us with a comprehensive and greatly simplified overview, facilitating a more coherent understanding of the forthcoming discussions within this publication.

		Curvature		
		YES	NO	
Momentum	YES	$a_{\mu\nu}$	$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv (c_{\mu\nu} + \Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$	$\frac{8 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D} \times g_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} + \Lambda \right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$
	NO	$c_{\mu\nu} \equiv (b_{\mu\nu} - \Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$	$d_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} \right)$	$\left(\frac{R}{2} - \Lambda \right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$
		$G_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$	$\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}$	$R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times g_{\mu\nu}$

Table 1. Four basic fields of nature and Einstein's field equations.

While following the framework of consistent reasoning and today established principles, we can augment the Einstein field equations with the as yet unknown tensor ($i \times g_{\mu\nu}$), preserving their origi-

nal form without alteration. Introducing this new tensor doesn't disrupt the logical coherence or mathematical integrity of the Einstein field equations (see equation 5), and does not lead to contradictory or illogical results within the established context of the equations and their application.

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_{\mu\nu} &\equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} && + && \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} + && 0 && + && 0 && + && \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4}\right) \times T_{\mu\nu} + (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
 &\equiv (G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) + (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
 &\equiv (G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) + 0 + (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
 &\equiv (G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} + (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
 &\equiv (G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} + (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} + (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \\
 &\equiv \underbrace{\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - (R \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (i \times g_{\mu\nu})}_{a_{\mu\nu}} + \underbrace{\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (i \times g_{\mu\nu})}_{b_{\mu\nu}} + \underbrace{\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - (i \times g_{\mu\nu})}_{c_{\mu\nu}} + \underbrace{(i \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})}_{d_{\mu\nu}} \\
 &\equiv && a_{\mu\nu} && + && b_{\mu\nu} && + && c_{\mu\nu} && + && d_{\mu\nu}
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

(Einstein, 1916, 1917)

Our efforts to address the problem of geometrizing all four fundamental fields of nature have led us to the realization that even an unfamiliar tensor, $i \times g_{\mu\nu}$, exerts minimal substantive influence on the essential aspects and relationships embedded within the Einstein field equations (see table 2).

		Curvature			
		YES		NO	
Momentum	YES	$a_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - (R \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (i \times g_{\mu\nu})$	$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (i \times g_{\mu\nu})$	$\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$	
	NO	$c_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$	$-(i \times g_{\mu\nu})$	$d_{\mu\nu} \equiv$	$-(\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$
		$G_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$		$\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu}$	$R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} \times g_{\mu\nu}$

Table 2. Einstein's field equations, the four basic fields of nature and the tensor $i \times g_{\mu\nu}$

In this vein, however, within the scope of these deductive deliberations, the Einstein field equations are deemed provisionally accurate. Nonetheless, it is the relationship between deduction and induction which lies at the core of any logical reasoning. Deduction in this context involves deriving specific conclusions from the general premise that the Einstein's field equations are mathematically correct, while moving from the general to the specific. In brief, experiments or providing empirical support in order to draw generalized conclusions from specific observations or instances and moving from the specific to the general (induction) is not of lesser importance. Both deduction and induction are fundamental scientific methods in constructing and validating scientific knowledge. However, deduction is characterized by certainty when the premises are true. Therefore, in this publication, we intend to bestow slightly greater attention upon the issue in question while referring to the hypothetico-deductive method.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Definitions

The relationship between objective reality and mathematical description or mathematical definition is one of the fundamental aspects of understanding the natural world. The objective existence of phenomena, objects, and processes in nature should be accompanied by an adequate mathematical description of various aspects of reality in order to provide accurate predictions and insights. However, we should always keep in mind that while mathematical models can provide powerful tools for understanding reality, they are ultimately abstractions that more or less simplify and idealize complex natural phenomena. In other words, the correspondence between mathematical descriptions and reality is not always one-to-one. Especially, the definitions are constructed to enable among other a clear communication and understanding among scientists. However, definitions might be inherently limited or assumptions in these definitions might prevent a perfect match with the intricacies of the real world. We cannot take the definitions for granted and need to check the same for the logical content. In essence, mathematics serves as one of our tools to explore, analyse, and predict the behaviour of the objective reality. Nonetheless, mathematics is not identical with objective reality itself. While mathematics is a valuable aid in our quest to understand the world, reality itself remains a complex, multifaceted entity that don't care at all about any mathematical representation.

2.1.1. Einstein field equation

Definition 2.1 (Einstein field equations). *The Einstein's field equations have been presented by equation 1.*

2.1.2. Four basic fields of nature

Definition 2.2 (Four basic fields of nature). *The four basic fields of nature have been presented by equation 3.*

2.1.3. Stress-energy tensor of matter

Definition 2.3 (Stress-energy tensor of matter). *The Stress-energy tensor of matter, denoted as $E_{\mu\nu}$, is determined by the basic fields of nature as*

$$a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) T_{\mu\nu} = E_{\mu\nu} \quad (6)$$

2.1.4. Tensor of non-energy

Definition 2.4 (Tensor of non-energy). *The tensor of non-energy, denoted as $\underline{E}_{\mu\nu}$, is determined by the basic fields of nature as*

$$c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) g_{\mu\nu} \right) - (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) = \underline{E}_{\mu\nu} \quad (7)$$

2.1.5. Einstein's tensor

Definition 2.5 (Tensor of non-energy). *Einstein's tensor, denoted as $G_{\mu\nu}$, is determined by the basic fields of nature as*

$$a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} \quad (8)$$

2.1.6. Anti Einstein's tensor

Definition 2.6 (Anti Einstein's tensor). *The anti Einstein's tensor, denoted as $\underline{G}_{\mu\nu}$, is determined by the basic fields of nature as*

$$b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) g_{\mu\nu} \right) = \underline{G}_{\mu\nu} \quad (9)$$

In contrast to the Einstein tensor which is a complex combination of the Ricci tensor and the metric tensor designed in a way that it capture the curvature of space-time and relating the same curvature of space-time to the distribution of energy and momentum through Einstein's field equations, the anti Einstein tensor, as the other of the Einstein tensor, is equally a mathematical operation involving the Ricci scalar R and the metric tensor.

2.1.7. The tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$

Definition 2.7 (The tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$).

The stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field (see [Misner et al., 1973](#), p. 140) describes the distribution of energy, momentum, and stress associated with the electromagnetic field. It captures the interactions between the electromagnetic field and space-time geometry, including contributions from both the electric and magnetic fields. The co-variant stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field with the inclusion of the electric constant μ_0 is given as

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) \quad (10)$$

where: $T_{\mu\nu}$ or $b_{\mu\nu}$ or $bg_{\mu\nu}$ is the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field, $F_{\mu\alpha}$ is the electromagnetic field tensor, F_{ν}^{α} is the dual electromagnetic field tensor, $g_{\mu\nu}$ is the metric tensor, $F_{\mu\nu}$

represents the components of the electromagnetic field tensor. The exact form of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field can vary slightly depending on the conventions used in different fields of physics. The electromagnetic field tensor $F_{\mu\nu}$, conventionally labelled F , is defined in component form as $F_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu A_\nu - \partial_\nu A_\mu$ where ∂ is the four-gradient and A is the four-potential. The same tensor can be re-written as $F_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{D} (g^{\mu\nu} (\partial_\mu A_\nu - \partial_\nu A_\mu)) g_{\mu\nu}$. In the following, let us simplify the formula of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field as

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_\nu^\alpha}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \right) \quad (11)$$

Proof. We start with the equation

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left[F_{\mu\alpha} F_\nu^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right] \quad (12)$$

Rearranging equation 12, it is

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left[\left(\left(\frac{D}{D} \right) F_{\mu\alpha} F_\nu^\alpha \right) - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right] \quad (13)$$

Simplifying, it is

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{\mu_0} \left[\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_\nu^\alpha}{D} \right) g_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) g_{\mu\nu} \right] \quad (14)$$

The stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field completely geometrized is given as

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_\nu^\alpha}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (15)$$

□

The equation before can be simplified further. The fundamental invariants of the electromagnetic field are scalar quantities that can be constructed from the electromagnetic field tensor $F_{\mu\nu}$ and its dual tensor. The first invariant F_1 is the square of the electromagnetic field tensor contracted with its dual tensor. The second invariant F_2 is the contraction of the electromagnetic field tensor with itself. The third invariant F_3 is the contraction of the dual tensor with itself. These invariants remain invariant under Lorentz transformations.

Corollary 2.1.

Geometrizing the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field is essential for achieving a consistent and unified description of all fundamental forces of nature within the framework of general relativity. This would enable us to treat electromagnetism on an equal footing with gravity, which is a fundamental aspect of modern theoretical physics. We provided already a geometrized form of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field (see equation 15) as

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (16)$$

This is a form of geometrization of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field in the context of general relativity, where the gravitational effects of matter and energy are described by the curvature of spacetime itself. So, in a sense, yes, this equation represents the geometrization of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field within the framework of general relativity. However, even if this equation is a valid expression for the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field in a curved spacetime, which incorporates the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ of the spacetime, equation 15 can be simplified further as

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0 \times 2 \times D} \left((2 \times |F|^2) - \left(D \times \left(\mathbf{B}^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \mathbf{E}^2 \right) \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (17)$$

Proof. We derived the equation

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (18)$$

As next we simplify the term $g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha}$. In index notation, repeated indices imply summation (Einstein's summation convention). This convention simplifies expressions involving tensors. In the expression $g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha}$, a repeated index is summed over, so that the same takes on all possible values, allowing for the contraction of a tensor. It is $g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} = F_{\alpha}^{\nu}$ and we do obtain

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{F_{\alpha}^{\nu} F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (19)$$

Nonetheless, the expression $F_{\alpha}^{\nu} F_{\nu}^{\alpha}$ represents the contraction (summation) of the indices ν and α for the tensor F. In terms of the Einstein summation convention, when an index appears both as a subscript and a superscript in a term, it implies summation over all possible values of that index. In other words, the expression $F_{\alpha}^{\nu} F_{\nu}^{\alpha}$ is equivalent to the sum of all the components of the tensor F, denoted as $|F|^2$. It is $g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} = F_{\alpha}^{\nu} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} = |F|^2$. Equation 19 becomes

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{|F|^2}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (20)$$

The value of the expression $F_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta}$ is determined by the components of the electromagnetic field tensor $F_{\mu\nu}$ and its dual and is given by:

$$F_{\alpha\beta}F^{\alpha\beta} = 2 \left(\mathbf{B}^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \mathbf{E}^2 \right) \quad (21)$$

where $\mathbf{B}^2$ represents the magnitude of the magnetic field vector $\mathbf{B}$, $\mathbf{E}^2$ represents the magnitude of the electric field vector $\mathbf{E}$ and c is the speed of light in vacuum. Equation 20 becomes

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{|F|^2}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{2 \left(\mathbf{B}^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \mathbf{E}^2 \right)}{4} \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (22)$$

or

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{|F|^2}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{\left(\mathbf{B}^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \mathbf{E}^2 \right)}{2} \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (23)$$

Rearranging equation 23 by $D = g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}$ and by the number 2, we obtain it is

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{2 \times |F|^2}{2 \times D} \right) - \left(\frac{D \times \left(\mathbf{B}^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \mathbf{E}^2 \right)}{2 \times D} \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (24)$$

In tensor calculus, it is not generally accepted to divide tensors directly, even if mathematically possible (see Barukčić, 2016b). In other words, division of tensors is not a standard operation, and other appropriate tensor operations are needed to obtain valid expressions. Thus far, equation 24 involves division by $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} = D$ in the denominator, which is potentially not defined and therefore worthless. However, the expression $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} = D$ is a scalar because it represents the contraction (or summation) of indices in a way that results in a scalar quantity. Therefore, in equation 24 we are dividing by a scalar and not by tensors. When you write $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}$, you are summing over repeated indices, following the Einstein summation convention. The indices μ and ν appear twice, once as subscripts and once as superscripts. This implies a sum over all possible values of these indices. When a contraction is performed, effectively each component of the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$ is multiplied by the corresponding component of the contravariant metric tensor $g^{\mu\nu}$ and then summing over all the components. In other words, we are summing scalar products of components and the result is itself a scalar value. Equation 24 is a valid expression. Simplifying equation 24, it is

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0 \times 2 \times D} \left((2 \times |F|^2) - \left(D \times \left(\mathbf{B}^2 - \frac{1}{c^2} \mathbf{E}^2 \right) \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (25)$$

Equation 25 is one possible and mathematically simplified expression of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field in the presence of gravity within the framework of general relativity.

□

However, even equation 25 can be simplified further. Under circumstances where $|F|^2 = \left(\mathbf{B}^2 - \frac{1}{c^2}\mathbf{E}^2\right)$ it follows that

$$b_{\mu\nu} = bg_{\mu\nu} = T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{(2-D)}{\mu_0 \times 2 \times D}\right) \times \left(\mathbf{B}^2 - \frac{1}{c^2}\mathbf{E}^2\right)\right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (26)$$

2.1.8. The tensor $d_{\mu\nu}$

Definition 2.8 (The tensor $d_{\mu\nu}$). *The tensor $d_{\mu\nu}$ is determined by the basic relationships as*

$$d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) - c_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) g_{\mu\nu}\right) - c_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) \equiv (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) - (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (27)$$

From these definitions follows that

$$c_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (i \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (28)$$

Under conditions where $(i \times g_{\mu\nu}) = 0$ it is $c_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) g_{\mu\nu}\right)$ but not in general.

2.1.9. The relationship between the tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$

Definition 2.9 (The relationship between the tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$). *The relationship between the tensor $b_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $c_{\mu\nu}$ is described by the equation*

$$c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) = b_{\mu\nu} \quad (29)$$

2.1.10. The relationship between the tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $d_{\mu\nu}$

Definition 2.10 (The relationship between the tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $d_{\mu\nu}$). *The relationship between the tensor $a_{\mu\nu}$ and the tensor $d_{\mu\nu}$ is described by the equation*

$$a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (Rg_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (30)$$

2.1.11. Space-time dimension D

Definition 2.11 (Space-time dimension D).

The Kronecker delta (see [Zehfuss, 1858](#)), a notation invented by Leopold Kronecker (1823-1891) in 1868 (see [Kronecker, 1868](#)), appears in many areas of physics, mathematics, and engineering. In general, the Kronecker delta, denoted as δ_{μ}^{ν} , is defined (see [Einstein, 1916](#), p. 787) as

$$g_{\mu\rho}g^{\nu\rho} \equiv g_{\mu}^{\nu} \equiv \delta_{\mu}^{\nu} \quad (31)$$

The expression $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}$ is not identical to the Kronecker delta δ_{μ}^{ν} . In the expression $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}$, the indices μ and ν are summed over, meaning they represent a contraction of two tensors, the Kronecker delta doesn't represent a contraction. In general relativity and differential geometry, $g_{\mu\nu}$ represents the components of the metric tensor, and $g^{\mu\nu}$ represents the components of its inverse. The expression $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}$ is a contraction involving these components and follows a common operation in tensor calculus known as the trace of a matrix. The contraction $g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}$ yields the dimensionality of the space-time, denoted as D . Therefore, in general, we define the dimensionality of the space-time D as

$$g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} \equiv D \quad (32)$$

where D might denote the number of space-time dimensions and $g^{\mu\nu}$ is the inverse metric tensor. In matrix notation for $D = 4$ space-time dimensions, this property can be represented as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} g_{00} & g_{01} & g_{02} & g_{03} \\ g_{10} & g_{11} & g_{12} & g_{13} \\ g_{20} & g_{21} & g_{22} & g_{23} \\ g_{30} & g_{31} & g_{32} & g_{33} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} g^{00} & g^{01} & g^{02} & g^{03} \\ g^{10} & g^{11} & g^{12} & g^{13} \\ g^{20} & g^{21} & g^{22} & g^{23} \\ g^{30} & g^{31} & g^{32} & g^{33} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} g_{00}g^{00} + g_{01}g^{10} + g_{02}g^{20} + g_{03}g^{30} & \dots \\ \dots & \dots \end{bmatrix} = 4 \quad (33)$$

and at the end eqally as

$$\begin{pmatrix} g_{00} & g_{10} & g_{20} & g_{30} \\ g_{01} & g_{11} & g_{21} & g_{31} \\ g_{02} & g_{12} & g_{22} & g_{32} \\ g_{03} & g_{13} & g_{23} & g_{33} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} g^{00} & g^{10} & g^{20} & g^{30} \\ g^{01} & g^{11} & g^{21} & g^{31} \\ g^{02} & g^{12} & g^{22} & g^{32} \\ g^{03} & g^{13} & g^{23} & g^{33} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} = 4 \quad (34)$$

Einstein field equations ([Einstein, 1915, 1916, 1935](#); [Einstein and Sitter, 1932](#)) were initially formulated by Einstein himself in the context of a four-dimensional theory even though Einstein field equations need not to break down under conditions of D space-time dimensions (see [Stephani, 2003](#)). Nonetheless, based on Einstein's statement ([Einstein, 1916](#), p. 796), one gets

$$g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} \equiv D \equiv +4 \quad (35)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}} \equiv \frac{1}{4} \quad (36)$$

where $g^{\mu\nu}$ is the matrix inverse of the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$. The inverse metric tensor or the metric tensor, which is always symmetric, allow tensors to be transformed into each other and are used to lower and raise indices. The inverse metric tensor $g^{\mu\nu}$ is of the same size as the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$. Thus far, whatever $g_{\mu\nu}$ does, $g^{\mu\nu}$ undoes and their product is the identity.

2.1.12. The tensor $i_{\mu\nu}$

The tensor $i_{\mu\nu}$ is defined by the relationship

$$i_{\mu\nu} = i \times g_{\mu\nu} = d_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{R}{2} g_{\mu\nu}\right) - c_{\mu\nu} \quad (37)$$

In point of fact, it's important to note that the determining parts of the Einstein's field equations are interdependent, and changing the value of one part like $i_{\mu\nu}$ will affect the consistency of the other parts (see table 3).

		Curvature		
		YES	NO	
Momentum	YES	$a_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (Rg_{\mu\nu}) + (ig_{\mu\nu})$	$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) g_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) - (ig_{\mu\nu})$	$\left(\frac{R}{D} g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} g_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu})$
	NO	$c_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) g_{\mu\nu} - (ig_{\mu\nu})$	$d_{\mu\nu} \equiv (ig_{\mu\nu}) - (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu})$	$\left(\frac{R}{2} g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu})$
		$G_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2}\right) g_{\mu\nu}$	$\frac{R}{2} g_{\mu\nu}$	$R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} g_{\mu\nu}$

Table 3. Einstein's field equations, the four basic fields of nature and the tensor $i \times g_{\mu\nu}$

In detail, it is (see equation 10)

$$\begin{aligned} i_{\mu\nu} &= ig_{\mu\nu} \\ &\equiv d_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} g_{\mu\nu}\right) - b_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) \\ &\equiv \left(\frac{R}{2} g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}\right)\right) + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) \end{aligned} \quad (38)$$

Nonetheless, based on the equations and definitions provided, it seem to be possible to find a specific value for $i_{\mu\nu}$ under circumstances where the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter vanish i.e. where $a_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (Rg_{\mu\nu}) + (ig_{\mu\nu}) = 0$. Under these circumstances it is thinkable, that the relationship

$$i_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{D-1}{D}\right) Rg_{\mu\nu} \quad (39)$$

might be valid where D is the space-time dimension. Under these conditions, the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field follows as

$$\left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}\right)\right) = \left(\frac{R}{2} g_{\mu\nu}\right) - \left(\left(\frac{D-1}{D}\right) Rg_{\mu\nu}\right) + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (40)$$

Whether the condition $a_{\mu\nu} = 0$ is an essential precondition of pure non-locality and might be discussed at another occasion. In toto, careful analysis is required to ensure that the equations are coherent and

		Curvature	
		YES	NO
Momentum	YES	$a_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D}g_{\mu\nu}\right) - (Rg_{\mu\nu}) + (0)$	$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{2}\right)g_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) - (0)$
	NO	$c_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{2}\right)g_{\mu\nu} - (0)$	$d_{\mu\nu} \equiv (0) - (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu})$
		$G_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2}\right)g_{\mu\nu}$	$R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{2}g_{\mu\nu}$
			$R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D}g_{\mu\nu}$

Table 4. Einstein's field equations, the four basic fields of nature and the tensor $i \times g_{\mu\nu}$

logically consistent. In general, for the given set of equations, $i_{\mu\nu}$ can take various values, including zero, and the Einstein's field equations are satisfied (see table 4).

However, under conditions where $i_{\mu\nu} = d_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{R}{2}g_{\mu\nu}\right) - c_{\mu\nu} = 0$ it is

$$d_{\mu\nu} = -(\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (41)$$

and

$$\left(\frac{R}{2}g_{\mu\nu}\right) = c_{\mu\nu} \quad (42)$$

A more specific value of $i_{\mu\nu}$ might require additional and more precise calculations which can help determine its value. Without further detailed calculations, $i_{\mu\nu}$ remains undetermined.

2.2. Axioms

2.2.1. Axiom I. Lex identitatis (Identity Law)

Are there at least two things which are completely like each other? Nonetheless, identity is identity and much more than this. Identity is determined in its own self as against non-identity. Nonetheless, identity as such is in its own self, non-identity too. Identity is the non-being of difference, a difference which immediately collapses within itself. Identity as determination of simple equality with itself in contrast to difference is equally a non-being as non-being of its own other. Identity in the positive is given as

$$+1 = +1 \quad (43)$$

However, identity is different, identity in its own self, in its very nature, is different. Identity as self-related negativity, as negativity of itself, determines itself while it is distinguished from difference, it is an identity in unity with difference. It is equally true that

$$-1 = -1 \quad (44)$$

Identity, seen as the vanishing of otherness and held to be separate from difference, is in its own self different and distinct from difference.

“... the law of identity ... is usually adduced as the first law of thought.”

(see [Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, 1812, 1813, 1816, 1991](#))

However, in the togetherness of both, difference as the unity of itself and identity, has its own other within itself, has not lost itself in its own other, but preserves itself in it. Opposition as the completion of difference is the unity and the conflict of identity and difference. As moments of opposition, identity and difference are different in one and the same identity and thus far are opposites. Noteworthy, in the year 1947, the Danish physicist Niels Henrik David Bohr (1885–1962) crafted a distinctive family coat of arms. The inscription upon Bohr’s familial emblem reads

contraria sunt complementa

(opposites are complements)

([Fierke, 2019](#); [Graubard, 1976](#))

However, opposites might cancel one another in their relation, so that the result of this interaction might end up at zero.

2.2.2. Axiom II. Lex contradictionis (Contradiction Law)

Identity with itself by excluding the negative, the other of itself, makes itself into the negative of what it excludes from itself, identity makes itself into its opposite. The law of contradiction is rather the opposite of the law of identity, it is equally the other of the law of identity. In general, it is

$$+0 = +1 - 1 = +1 \quad (45)$$

or in the negative

$$-0 = -1 \quad (46)$$

The Latin phrase **ex falso sequitur quodlibet** translates to something like **from a falsehood, anything follows**. The dogma *ex falso sequitur quodlibet* claims that when the chain of thoughts is beginning with a false premise or statement (see equation 45), any conclusion or statement from the same can be derived, whether true or false. In more simple words, if you start with a false assumption, you can logically prove anything you want, regardless of whether it’s actually true or makes sense. It is indeed necessary to underscore the importance of ensuring that the premises or assumptions in logical reasoning are accurate and valid. However, conclusions drawn from false premises (see equation 45) cannot lead to any result you want, but, in the absence of negation or of (technical) errors, only to a

contradiction. In general, axiom I (lex identitatis) preserves at all cost the truth (see equation 43), while axiom II (lex contradictionis) preserves at all cost the falsity, the contradiction (see equation 45). Historically, the dogma **ex falso sequitur quodlibet** was discussed by various philosophers and logicians over the centuries. Meanwhile, ex falso sequitur quodlibet is refuted. Ex falso sequitur quodlibet has its origins in ancient Greek and medieval logic, but is most notably associated with the work of the Greek philosopher Aristotle (384–322 BCE). Aristotle discussed ex falso sequitur quodlibet in the context of his logical treatises, where he explored the consequences of false premises in deductive reasoning. The Latin phrase **ex falso sequitur quodlibet** itself is attributed to the medieval philosopher and theologian Thomas Aquinas (1225–1274), who incorporated it into his discussions of logic and metaphysics.

2.2.3. Axiom III. Lex negationis (Negation Law)

It is

$$\neg(+0) = +1 \quad (47)$$

while $\neg$ is the (logical, natural et cetera) negation.

3. Results

3.1. The Ricci tensor

The Ricci tensor provides information about the local curvature of space-time in general relativity and can be expressed in terms of the metric tensor and the Christoffel symbols of the Levi-Civita connection (also known as the Christoffel connection). The Levi-Civita connection is the unique metric-compatible and torsion-free connection associated with a given metric tensor. The inherent complexity of the curvature of spacetime and the fundamental mathematical structure and geometric information encoded in the Ricci tensor makes it challenging to express the Ricci tensor as a scalar multiple of the metric tensor in the general case. In other words, it is very difficult to relate the Ricci tensor and the metric tensor through scalar. If at all, such a scalar should satisfy certain mathematical relationships and properties.

Theorem 1.

In general, it is

$$S \times g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{R}{D} \times g_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} \quad (48)$$

Proof by direct proof. To summarize, the curvature information contained in the Ricci tensor can be fully captured by a simple scalar-metric relationship as

$$R_{\mu\nu} = S \times g_{\mu\nu} \quad (49)$$

where S is a scalar on unknown properties. However, a scalar don't need to be constant. Taking the trace of the Ricci tensor provides a scalar quantity that captures a measure of the overall curvature of space-time at a given point. Taking the trace, it is

$$R_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} = S \times g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} \quad (50)$$

The trace of the Ricci tensor plays a significant role in understanding the relationship between curvature and the stress-energy content of space-time. Equation 50 can be simplified as

$$R = S \times D \quad (51)$$

The Ricci tensor involves second derivatives of the metric tensor due to the presence of the Christoffel symbols, which are constructed from first derivatives of the metric tensor. The Christoffel symbols represent the connection coefficients of the Levi-Civita connection, which is the metric-compatible and torsion-free connection associated with the metric tensor. These second derivatives of the metric tensor contribute to the geometric curvature of spacetime. The Ricci tensor involves second derivatives of the metric tensor (through the Christoffel symbols). More or less, the scalar times the metric tensor involves only first derivatives. Therefore, it is not possible to express the Ricci tensor as a scalar times the metric tensor. However, it is appropriate to address this potential confusion more accurately.

Again, the Ricci tensor involves second derivatives of the metric tensor due to the presence of the Christoffel symbols, which are constructed from first derivatives of the metric tensor. The Christoffel symbols represent the connection coefficients of the Levi-Civita connection, which is the metric-compatible and torsion-free connection associated with the metric tensor. These second derivatives of the metric tensor contribute to the geometric curvature of spacetime. On the other hand, a scalar times the metric tensor can indeed involve second derivatives of the metric tensor, depending on how the scalar is constructed. The statement that a scalar times the metric tensor involves only first derivatives is not generally accurate. This is because the behaviour of derivatives depends on the specific expression of the scalar function. **Counter-example I.** Vacuum solutions of the Einstein field equations in general relativity with a cosmological constant involves such a scalar term where the cosmological constant term contributes to the overall curvature and can involve both first and second derivatives of the metric tensor. **Counter-example II.** A scalar times the metric tensor does not necessarily involve only first derivatives. The metric tensor itself can depend on the second derivatives of the metric coefficients with respect to the coordinates. Therefore, when a scalar is multiplied by the metric tensor, the resulting expression can involve second derivatives of the scalar field with respect to the coordinates. This is particularly relevant in the context of general relativity, where the Einstein field equations involve terms like the Ricci tensor and the Ricci scalar, which are constructed from second derivatives of the metric tensor. In essence, the key point is that the behaviour of derivatives depends on the specific form of the scalar function and the context in which it is used. Scalars can involve second derivatives of the metric tensor, if necessary for the mathematical expression to accurately represent the underlying physics. Taking the trace of the Ricci tensor as done before provide us with a scalar quantity which is able to capture the overall curvature of spacetime at a given point as

$$S = \frac{R}{D} \quad (52)$$

Equation 52 is multiplied by the metric tensor. In general, the Ricci tensor expressed as a scalar times the metric tensor is given as

$$S \times g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{R}{D} g_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} \quad (53)$$

□

Equation 53 could have significant implications for the geometry and curvature of space-time. Expressing the Ricci tensor as a scalar multiple of the metric tensor would simplify the mathematical formulation of the Einstein field equations. However, the rich and varied geometric properties that arise from the full curvature tensor are not lost by this simplification of the Ricci tensor. Nonetheless, the Ricci tensor expressed as a scalar multiple of the metric tensor does not imply that the curvature of spacetime is constant everywhere or that every point in space-time has the same curvature. In many cases, the complexity of the full Ricci tensor is necessary to accurately model phenomena like gravitational waves, black holes, and the detailed dynamics of spacetime. Nonetheless, while simplification provided is useful for gaining insights and making calculations more manageable, it's crucial to point out that besides the level of simplification chosen, the essential physics of the system being studied is completely captured. While the Einstein field equations would become simpler, they still accurately describe the full complexity of how matter and energy influence the curvature of spacetime even if

many phenomena in general relativity, such as gravitational waves and black holes, require the full curvature tensor to be accurately described. In point of fact, it's important to explore alternative theoretical frameworks. However, any departure from the known would need to be accompanied by robust theoretical justifications, empirical evidence, and experimental confirmation. Mathematically, equation 53 is correct. However, if it is forbidden to equate Ricci tensor and metric as done in equation 49, the same is not of use. The current experimental and observational methods are based on the assumption of a more or less constant space-time dimension. The prevailing understanding especially in general relativity is that space-time is a smooth manifold with a fixed dimension. In contrast to general relativity, equation 53 appears to enable us and to demand the possibility of a space-time dimension which is changing (even from point to point) in order to obtain a detailed information about how space-time is curved due to matter and energy. However, experimental tests are required to verify or falsify equation 53.

To address again the question about the consequences of **a changing space-time dimension**, let us consider view points. In general, a changing space-time dimension could potentially have implications for a wide range of physical phenomena, including gravitational interactions, particle physics, and cosmology. Any variations in the dimension of space-time could require new experimental techniques and observations to detect and measure these changes. Equation 53 which does not forbid the varying space-time dimension would need to be consistent with known experimental results. Introducing a varying space-time dimension could significantly complicate the mathematical and theoretical framework of physics. The equations of motion, field equations, and all physical laws would need to be reformulated to account for the changing dimension. In the context of general relativity, space-time is treated as a smooth and continuous manifold with a fixed dimension. In the standard Einstein field equations, the curvature is determined by the distribution of matter and energy, leading to variable curvature in different regions of space-time. Under conditions of general relativity an besides of the variable curvature in different regions of space-time, **the space-time dimension itself is constant** and might be understood to some extent as a preferred or even absolute frame of reference. Nonetheless, in modern physics, the notion of a preferred frame of reference has been replaced by the principle of relativity, which has been confirmed by numerous experimental observations and is a foundational concept in today's understanding of the physical universe. In the theory of special relativity developed by Albert Einstein, there is no preferred frame of reference in the sense that all inertial frames are considered equally valid for describing physical phenomena. In the theory of general relativity, which extends the principles of special relativity to include gravity and acceleration, there is also no preferred frame of reference. Gravitational effects are described by the curvature of spacetime, and all observers, regardless of their locations and motions, follow paths (geodesics) determined by this curvature. We may need to point out the theoretical danger that **a concept of a varying space-time dimension** could require a significant departure from the established principles of the theory of general relativity. A scenario where the scalar curvature is a constant multiple of the space-time dimension is an interesting mathematical exploration. Unfortunately, the same scenario deviates significantly from the well-established principles of general relativity. The answer to the question becomes more and more pressing to the reader, is the dimension of space-time D changing, even from point to point?

3.2. The stress-energy tensor of matter

According to Einstein, it is necessary to consider the fundamental relationship between ordinary matter and the electromagnetic field.

“... a tensor, $T_{\mu\nu}$, of the second rank ... includes in itself the energy density of the electromagnetic field and of ponderable matter; we shall denote this in the following as the ‘energy tensor of matter’”

(Einstein, 1923, pp. 87/88)

Theorem 2.

In general, the stress-energy tensor of matter is determined as

$$(a_{\mu\nu}) + (b_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) \quad (54)$$

Proof by direct proof. It is

$$\left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) = \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) \quad (55)$$

or

$$(a_{\mu\nu}) + \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) - (a_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) \quad (56)$$

We define in general that

$$(b_{\mu\nu}) \equiv \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) - (a_{\mu\nu}) \quad (57)$$

The stress-energy tensor of matter is determined by the relationship

$$(a_{\mu\nu}) + (b_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) \quad (58)$$

□

Einstein defined the relationship between ordinary matter ($a_{\mu\nu}$) and electromagnetic field ($b_{\mu\nu}$) as follows.

“Wir unterscheiden im folgenden zwischen ‘Gravitationsfeld’ und ‘Materie’, in dem Sinne, daß **alles außer dem Gravitationsfeld als ‘Materie’ bezeichnet** wird, also nicht nur die ‘Materie’ im üblichen Sinne, sondern auch das elektromagnetische Feld. ”

(Einstein, 1916, p. 802/803)

Einstein's position translated into English: "In the subsequent discussion, a distinction is drawn between the 'gravitational field' and 'matter', wherein everything except the gravitational field is denoted as 'matter', encompassing not only 'matter' in the conventional sense but also the electromagnetic field." In other words, the demarcation delineated by Einstein elucidates all entities beyond the gravitational field are encompassed under the term 'matter' whereby 'matter' itself is categorized into the 'matter' in the conventional sense and into the electromagnetic field. While not traditionally considered material, Einstein subsumed the electromagnetic field within this comprehensive conception of 'matter'. The following and only symbolic figure might illustrate the relationship between 'matter' in the conventional sense and the electromagnetic field in more detail.

Electromagnetic field ($b_{\mu\nu}$)

Ordinary Matter ($a_{\mu\nu}$)

($E_{\mu\nu}$)

The stress-energy tensor of matter, ($E_{\mu\nu}$), "Considered phenomenologically, this energy tensor is composed of that of the electromagnetic field and of matter in the narrower sense." (see also [Einstein, 1923](#), p. 93) In general, the stress energy tensor of ordinary matter, $a_{\mu\nu}$, is given as

$$a_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) \quad (59)$$

Vranceanu ([Vranceanu, 1936](#)) is elaborating on the same issue too. The energy tensor T_{kl} is treated by Vranceanu as the sum of two tensors one of which is due to the electromagnetic field ($b_{\mu\nu}$).

"On peut aussi supposer que le tenseur d'énergie T_{kl} soit la somme de deux tenseurs dont un dû au champ électromagnétique..." ([Vranceanu, 1936](#))

In English: 'One can also assume that the energy tensor T_{kl} be the sum of two tensors one of which is due to the electromagnetic field.' It is (see equation 59)

$$a_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times \left(\frac{D}{D} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) \quad (60)$$

or

$$a_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) \quad (61)$$

According to equation 15, it is

$$a_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (62)$$

and at the end

$$a_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (63)$$

Einstein makes a clear distinction between the **gravitational field** and **matter** and defines the gravitational field ex negativo as all but matter or in German: “**alles außer dem Gravitationsfeld als ‘Materie’ bezeichnet**”. It is important to note that matter in the sense of Einstein encompasses not only the conventional meaning of matter but also includes electromagnetic fields as such. In other words, Einstein is using a broader definition of matter to include not only particles and substances but also the electromagnetic field itself. So, when Einstein mentions “die ‘Materie’ im üblichen Sinne,” he’s essentially referring to the conventional or everyday notion of matter as physical substances, but Einstein is extending this definition to include the electromagnetic field within the scope of his understanding and definition of matter. By performing the subtraction of the stress-energy tensor of the electromagnetic field from the stress-energy tensor of matter which includes both, matter in the ordinary sense and electromagnetic fields, we obtain the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter. In other words, while removing the contribution of the electromagnetic field’s stress-energy from the stress-energy tensor of matter, we essentially isolate the contribution of electromagnetic fields from the total stress-energy content, leaving behind only the ordinary matter-related contribution (see equation 63). Geometrizing the stress-energy tensor of matter (see equation 1) and of ordinary matter (see equation 63) has several theoretical consequences. By geometrizing the stress-energy tensor of matter, we incorporate matter’s effects directly into the space-time curvature. This unification allows gravity to be described as the curvature of space-time caused by mass and energy, providing among other a geometric interpretation of gravitational interactions. The geometrization derived should be of use for the prediction and explanation of various gravitational phenomena, such as the bending of light by gravity (gravitational lensing), the precession of planetary orbits (like Mercury’s), and the existence of black holes. The geometrization of the stress-energy tensor of matter (see equation 1) is essential in cosmology, where it describes the large-scale structure and dynamics of the whole universe. Unification of the fundamental forces in nature remains one of the most profound challenges in modern theoretical physics. Unifying all the forces of nature is an extremely challenging task. While geometrizing gravity has been highly successful in general relativity, extending this approach to incorporate other forces, especially at quantum scales, poses substantial difficulties. In general relativity, the stress-energy tensor of matter plays a central role in describing how matter and energy curve spacetime, giving rise to the gravitational field. The complete geometrization of the energy-momentum tensor of matter (see equation 1) is a novel and fundamental concept that should fundamentally reshape our understanding of gravity, bearing the strategic potential to significantly diminish a substantial portion of our hunt for a unified field theory.

3.3. The tensor of non energy

Theorem 3.

In general, the tensor of non energy, denoted as $\underline{E}_{\mu\nu}$, is determined as

$$c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \underline{E}_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (64)$$

Proof by direct proof. In general, it is

$$a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} \quad (65)$$

or (see theorem 2)

$$c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - (a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu}) = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) \quad (66)$$

The tensor of non energy, $c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$, is determined as

$$c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \underline{E}_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \right) = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) - ((\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) \quad (67)$$

□

The following summary overview (see table 5) shall present before us the insights that have been hitherto secured.

		Curvature		
		YES	NO	
Momentum	YES	$a_{\mu\nu}$	$b_{\mu\nu}$	$\underline{E}_{\mu\nu}$
	NO	$c_{\mu\nu}$	$d_{\mu\nu}$	$\underline{E}_{\mu\nu}$
				$R_{\mu\nu}$

Table 5. The four basic fields of nature

Thus far, we have managed to secure certain insights. Regrettably, at the present juncture, the precise knowledge of the tensors $a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu}$ and of the tensors $b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$ remains uncertain to us.

3.4. The anti Einstein tensor I

Theorem 4.

In general, the anti Einstein tensor is given as

$$b_{\mu\nu} + y_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) \quad (68)$$

Proof by direct proof. It is

$$\left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) \quad (69)$$

or equally

$$b_{\mu\nu} + \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) - b_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) \quad (70)$$

We define an unknown preliminary tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$ as

$$y_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) - b_{\mu\nu} \quad (71)$$

The anti Einstein tensor is given as

$$b_{\mu\nu} + y_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) \quad (72)$$

□

At this point it is pertinent to note that we can be reasonably certain that an unknown tensor, denoted as $y_{\mu\nu}$, also determines the tensor $\left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right)$. However, our current understanding of the tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$ remains rather limited. As we transition from the realm of the known to the realm of the unknown, our intent is to endeavor to unveil the mysteries held by the tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$, to the extent that such an endeavor is feasible, if at all.

3.5. The anti Einstein tensor II

The tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$ is in our opinion at the same time an essential part of the tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$ and determines this tensor too.

Theorem 5.

In general, the anti Einstein tensor is given as

$$y_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) - ((\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) \quad (73)$$

Proof by direct proof. The tensor of non-energy is equal to itself. It is

$$\left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) - ((\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) - ((\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) \quad (74)$$

or

$$c_{\mu\nu} + \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) - ((\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) - c_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) - ((\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) \quad (75)$$

Given the accurate supposition that the tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$ forms an indispensable element of the tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu} - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})$, the ensuing definition promptly ensues. We establish the following definition:

$$y_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) - ((\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) - c_{\mu\nu} \quad (76)$$

The tensor of non-energy is given as

$$c_{\mu\nu} + y_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) - ((\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) \quad (77)$$

□

However, we don't know anything about the unknown preliminary tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$. At an initial glance, it appears to be that we have not drawn significantly closer to the resolution of our predicament.

3.6. The anti Einstein tensor III

The assumption that the tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$ is an essential component of the tensor $\left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right)\right) - ((\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}))$ is not proven. As is generally known, an assumption is not a proof, it is simply an assumption which can be true but need not. Therefore, it needs the proof that the tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$ is in reality indeed an essential part of the tensor $\left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right)\right) - ((\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}))$.

Theorem 6.

In general, the tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$ is an essential part of the tensors $c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$. It is

$$c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = b_{\mu\nu} + y_{\mu\nu} - ((\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) \quad (78)$$

Proof by direct proof. It is (see equation 67)

$$c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right)\right) - ((\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) \quad (79)$$

Based on equation 72, we obtain

$$c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = b_{\mu\nu} + y_{\mu\nu} - ((\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) \quad (80)$$

As can be seen, the tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$ is an essential part of the tensors $c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}$. The assumption is proofed. $\square$

3.7. The anti Einstein tensor IV

Theorem 7.

The unknown tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$ is determined in detail as

$$y_{\mu\nu} = d_{\mu\nu} \quad (81)$$

Proof by direct proof. The tensor of non energy, denoted as $\underline{E}_{\mu\nu}$, is determined as (see equation 64)

$$\underline{E}_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right)\right) - ((\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu})) = c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} \quad (82)$$

Based on equation 77, we obtain the following relationship.

$$c_{\mu\nu} + y_{\mu\nu} = c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} \quad (83)$$

We obtain the generally valid relationship that

$$y_{\mu\nu} = d_{\mu\nu} \quad (84)$$

$\square$

3.8. The determination of the tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$

Theorem 8.

The tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$ is determined as

$$b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) \quad (85)$$

Proof by direct proof. The tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$ (see equation 68) is given as

$$b_{\mu\nu} + y_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) \quad (86)$$

The tensor $y_{\mu\nu}$ has been determined as $y_{\mu\nu} = d_{\mu\nu}$ (see equation 84). The tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$ is determined as

$$b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) \right) \quad (87)$$

□

After navigating through various confusions and complexities, and traversing intricate paths, we have successfully identified the tensor $\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$ in detail. The following overview is intended to deepen our current knowledge.

		Curvature		
		YES	NO	
Momentum	YES	$a_{\mu\nu}$	$b_{\mu\nu}$	$\underline{E}_{\mu\nu}$
	NO	$c_{\mu\nu}$	$d_{\mu\nu}$	$\underline{E}_{\mu\nu}$
		$\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$		$R_{\mu\nu}$

Table 6. The four basic fields of nature

3.9. The determination of Einstein's tensor $G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$

Theorem 9.

The Einstein's tensor is determined as

$$a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) = G_{\mu\nu} \quad (88)$$

Proof by direct proof. In general, it is (see equation 3)

$$a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} \quad (89)$$

or

$$a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - (b_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu}) \quad (90)$$

Using equation 87, we obtain

$$a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}\right) = G_{\mu\nu} \quad (91)$$

□

The following overview (see table 7) is designed to give us the necessary understanding of what has been achieved so far.

		Curvature		
		YES	NO	
Momentum	YES	$a_{\mu\nu}$	$b_{\mu\nu}$	$E_{\mu\nu}$
	NO	$c_{\mu\nu}$	$d_{\mu\nu}$	$\underline{E}_{\mu\nu}$
		$G_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$	$\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) \times g_{\mu\nu}$	$R_{\mu\nu}$

Table 7. The four basic fields of nature

The detailed interrelation among the four fundamental natural fields $a_{\mu\nu}, b_{\mu\nu}, c_{\mu\nu}, d_{\mu\nu}$ is outlined and recognized. Nonetheless, within this publication, the specific geometric composition of each distinct field ($a_{\mu\nu}, b_{\mu\nu}, c_{\mu\nu}, d_{\mu\nu}$) remains entirely elusive to our understanding. At present, our knowledge lacks the precise details regarding the intricate geometric arrangement characterizing these individual fields. It is to be noted that the Einstein tensor, denoted as $G_{\mu\nu}$, is a fundamental mathematical construct in the field of General Relativity, a theory proposed by Albert Einstein to describe gravity's effects on the curvature of space-time. The Einstein tensor encapsulates the geometric essence of space-time curvature resulting from mass and energy distributions. Mathematically, the Einstein

tensor is derived from the Ricci curvature tensor $R_{\mu\nu}$ and the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$, which together encapsulate the curvature of space-time. In essence, the Einstein tensor describes how the curvature of space-time is influenced by the distribution of mass and energy. In other words, the Einstein tensor is determined by the distribution of mass and energy. The tensor's components provide information about the curvature at each point in space-time and how it varies in different directions. Through Einstein's field equations, the Einstein tensor ($G_{\mu\nu}$) equates to the energy-momentum tensor which itself is representing the distribution of energy and momentum in space-time. This elegant relationship reflects the central tenet of General Relativity: mass and energy dictate the curvature of space-time, and in return, this curvature determines how objects move in the presence of gravity. The Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$ acts in this sense as a bridge between the distribution of mass and energy in the universe and the resulting gravitational effects. By understanding the tensor's properties and behavior, physicists might gain some insights into how massive objects influence space-time's curvature, leading to the observed gravitational interactions that govern celestial dynamics on both cosmic and local scales.

3.10. The determination of the tensors $c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = b_{\mu\nu}$

Theorem 10.

In general, it is

$$c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = b_{\mu\nu} \quad (92)$$

Proof by direct proof. The Einstein's field equations (see equation 1) are defined as

$$G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = \left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G}{c^4} \right) \times T_{\mu\nu} \quad (93)$$

This equation can be simplified as

$$a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = a_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} \quad (94)$$

and as

$$c_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) = b_{\mu\nu} \quad (95)$$

□

3.11. The determination of the tensors $a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu}$

Theorem 11.

In general, it is

$$a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - (R \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (96)$$

Proof by direct proof. It is

$$a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} = a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} \quad (97)$$

or (see equation 58 and equation 87)

$$a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) - b_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} \right) \quad (98)$$

Equation (98) simplifies as

$$a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} = G_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (99)$$

In general, it is

$$a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - (R \times g_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (100)$$

□

3.12. The cosmological constant and space-time dimensions

In the Einstein field equations, the term $(\Lambda g_{\mu\nu})$ represents the contribution of the cosmological constant (Λ) to the curvature of space-time, which affects the overall geometry of the universe. Originally introduced by Einstein (see also Einstein, 1917) to achieve a stationary universe and counterbalancing the attractive effects of gravity, its significance has evolved over time. In modern cosmology, (Λ) is associated with dark energy, which itself seems to be causing the accelerated expansion of the universe and is associated with empty space.

Theorem 12.

Nonetheless, the term $(\Lambda g_{\mu\nu})$ can be calculated as

$$\Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) + \left(\frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4 \times D} \times T \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (101)$$

Proof by direct proof. The standard form of the Einstein field equations in covariant notation is

$$(G_{\mu\nu}) + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) = (R_{\mu\nu}) - \left(\frac{R}{2} g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) = \frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} \quad (102)$$

Here, π is the mathematical constant pi, $G_{\mu\nu}$ is the Einstein tensor, which describes the curvature of space-time due to gravity, and $T_{\mu\nu}$ is the energy-momentum tensor, which describes the distribution of matter and energy in space-time. Equation 102 relates the curvature of space-time to the presence of matter and energy. In component form, the Einstein field equations are often written as a set of ten coupled differential equations, with each equation describing a specific component of the curvature tensor and its relationship to the energy-momentum tensor. Taking the trace of equation 102, it is

$$(R_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu}) - \left(\frac{R}{2} g_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu}) = \frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu} \quad (103)$$

or

$$(R) - \left(\frac{R}{2} \times D \right) + (\Lambda \times D) = \frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4} \times T \quad (104)$$

Here, $g_{\mu\nu} g^{\mu\nu} = D$ is the space-time dimension, $T = T_{\mu}^{\mu} = g^{\mu\nu} T_{\mu\nu}$ is Laue's scalar. The Laue scalar defined as $T = T_{\mu}^{\mu} = g^{\mu\nu} T_{\mu\nu}$ is the trace of the stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ and has a significant physical meaning in the context of general relativity and the Einstein field equations. In essence, the Laue scalar provides a measure of the effective energy density and momentum density in a given region of space-time. Thus far, rearranging equation 104, we obtain

$$(\Lambda \times D) = \left(\frac{R}{2} \times D \right) - R + \left(\frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4} \times T \right) \quad (105)$$

and the value of the cosmological constant is given as

$$\Lambda = \left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{R}{D} \right) + \left(\frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4 \times D} \times T \right) \quad (106)$$

Under conditions where $T = T_{\mu}^{\mu} = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu}$ becomes zero, the trace of the stress-energy tensor $T_{\mu\nu}$ vanishes or in other words, the sum of the energy density and the three momentum densities in all directions is balanced in a way that the net contribution cancels out. This could correspond to scenarios where matter and energy are distributed in a symmetric or balanced manner, resulting in a cancellation of their overall contributions to the curvature of space-time. In point of fact, if $T = T_{\mu}^{\mu} = g^{\mu\nu}T_{\mu\nu} = 0$, then the source of curvature (described by $T_{\mu\nu}$) is not present in a certain region of space-time. However, under these circumstances, the curvature of spacetime in that region would be determined solely by the cosmological constant term as

$$\Lambda = \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) + (0) \quad (107)$$

and not by the distribution of matter and energy. In other words, in the absence of matter and energy sources ($T_{\mu\nu} = 0$) in a vacuum solution of the Einstein field equations the curvature of space-time is primarily determined by other factors (see equation 107). The determination of the value of the cosmological constant (Λ) is a topic of extensive research in cosmology, and there are several experimental and observational approaches (Supernovae Observations, Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) Radiation, Gravitational Lensing) et cetera used to estimate its value. Multiplying equation 106 by the metric tensor of Einstein's general theory of relativity, it is

$$\Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) g_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) g_{\mu\nu} + \left(\frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4 \times D} \times T\right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (108)$$

or

$$\Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) + \left(\frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4 \times D} \times T\right)\right) g_{\mu\nu} \quad (109)$$

□

Unfortunately, we cannot avoid pointing out a few fundamental problems with equation 109 developed here. In a very special way, according to equation 109 the term ($\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}$) in the Einstein field equations depends on the space-time dimension ($D = g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}$) as $\Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) + \left(\frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4 \times D} \times T\right)\right) g_{\mu\nu}$. In last consequence, we have to accept, that the cosmological constant itself varies with the number of space-time dimensions. This has dramatic and significant implications for our understanding of the fundamental nature of space-time and its curvature and could pose various theoretical challenges for cosmologists and physicists working on understanding the nature of space-time and its interactions with matter and energy. As an example, the cosmological constant is often associated with dark energy, which is responsible for the observed accelerated expansion of the universe. A dimensional dependence of dark energy might imply that the nature of dark energy could change depending on the dimensionality of space-time which could have profound implications for our understanding of the origin and behaviour of dark energy. There are theories in cosmology, such as string theory and multiverse scenarios, which suggest the existence of multiple universes with different properties, including different space-time dimensions. A cosmological constant (Λ) which depends on space-time dimension might provide a potential mechanism to differentiate between universes with varying dimensionality. Furthermore, a (Λ) which is dimension-dependent could

potentially provide constraints on the values of fundamental constants and the relationships between them which would have implications for theories seeking to unify fundamental forces. The Equivalence Principle is a cornerstone of general relativity, asserting that the effects of gravity are indistinguishable from acceleration. A dimension-dependent (Λ) might challenge this principle, introducing a preferred reference frame tied to space-time dimension. As of now, the cosmological constant is usually treated as a constant term in the Einstein field equations, and there is not even a hint of experimental evidence supporting its dependence on space-time dimension.

3.13. The relationship between Λ and Anti Λ

Theorem 13.

The relationship between Λ and anti Λ is determined as

$$(\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) + (\underline{\Lambda} g_{\mu\nu}) = (R g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (110)$$

Proof by direct proof. The value of the cosmological constant given as

$$\Lambda = \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) + \left(\frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4 \times D} \times T\right) \quad (111)$$

doesn't change if we rearrange this equation slightly. We obtain

$$\Lambda = \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) + \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) + \left(\frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4 \times D} \times T\right) \quad (112)$$

or in other words

$$\Lambda = (R) - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{D}\right) + \left(\frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4 \times D} \times T\right) \quad (113)$$

Simplifying equation 113, it is

$$\Lambda = R - \left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4 \times D} \times T\right)\right) \quad (114)$$

Here, R is the Ricci scalar. In general, we define anti lambda (see Barukčić, 2013), denoted as ($\underline{\Lambda}$), which counteract the effects of the standard cosmological constant by the relationship

$$\underline{\Lambda} = \left(\left(\frac{R}{D}\right) - \left(\frac{R}{2}\right) - \left(\frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4 \times D} \times T\right)\right) \quad (115)$$

Equation 114 becomes

$$\Lambda = R - \underline{\Lambda} \quad (116)$$

In general, it is

$$\Lambda + \underline{\Lambda} = R \quad (117)$$

Multiplying equation 117 by the metric tensor, it is

$$(\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) + (\underline{\Lambda} g_{\mu\nu}) = (R g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (118)$$

□

However, regions of space-time where the Ricci scalar R , the contraction of the Ricci tensor, which represents the local curvature of space-time, is zero, are referred to as Ricci-flat regions. This condition is closely related to the vacuum solutions of Einstein's field equations, which describe space-time in the absence of matter and energy. In other words, in a vacuum, the curvature is determined solely by the presence of space-time itself, rather than the distribution of matter and energy. Such manifolds are geometrically flat in the sense that the curvature due to matter and energy is absent. Equation 118 describes the curvature of space-time in the absence of matter (the vacuum solutions) and is related to non-locality. The vacuum solutions are of use to understand the geometrical properties of space-time itself. Thus far, under conditions where $(R g_{\mu\nu} = 0)$ equation 118 becomes

$$+(\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}) = -(\underline{\Lambda} g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (119)$$

and we have the identity of a positive and a negative. Empty space, or what we commonly refer to as vacuum, is not truly empty in the sense of having absolutely no properties. Instead, even in a seemingly empty region of space, there might exist underlying fields that contribute to what we call vacuum. The equation 117 can be rearranged as

$$\frac{\Lambda}{R} + \frac{\underline{\Lambda}}{R} = \frac{R}{R} = 1 \quad (120)$$

Multiplying equation 120 by the term $\left(\frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4 \times D} \times T\right) \times \Psi$ where Ψ is the wave-function, we obtain a simple wave equation as

$$\left(\frac{\Lambda \times \left(\frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4 \times D} \times T\right)}{R} \times \Psi\right) + \left(\frac{\underline{\Lambda} \times \left(\frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4 \times D} \times T\right)}{R} \times \Psi\right) = \left(\frac{8 \times G \times \pi}{c^4 \times D} \times T\right) \times \Psi \quad (121)$$

Equation 117 can be rearranged. We obtain

$$\Lambda = R \times \left(1 - \frac{\underline{\Lambda}}{R}\right) \quad (122)$$

The cosmological constant passes over into the anti cosmological constant and vice versa. It is equally

$$\underline{\Lambda} = R \times \left(1 - \frac{\Lambda}{R}\right) \quad (123)$$

In our current understanding of cosmology, the introduction of an anti-cosmological constant is highly speculative and hypothetical and would require a significant departure from our current theoretical framework and would need to be supported by strong observational evidence, which is not the case

at present. In point of fact, especially observational cosmology would need to account for the effects of the anti-cosmological constant. Under the assumption of the existence of anti cosmological constant, the observable universe, including the cosmic microwave background radiation and the red-shift of distant galaxies, would show different characteristics compared to our universe. The presence of an anti-cosmological constant would influence the dynamics of stars, galaxies, and other astrophysical objects. It might lead to different patterns of star formation, galaxy evolution, and black hole dynamics. In other words, the presence of an anti-cosmological constant would significantly alter the cosmological evolution of the universe. Galaxies, galaxy clusters, and the large-scale structure of the cosmos would develop differently compared to our universe. Nonetheless, such a modification is logically consistent but need to be consistent with existing and new observational data.

3.14. The determination of the tensor $(a_{\mu\nu}) + (d_{\mu\nu})$

Theorem 14.

In general, it is

$$a_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (124)$$

Proof by direct proof. It is

$$a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} \quad (125)$$

or

$$a_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - b_{\mu\nu} - c_{\mu\nu} \quad (126)$$

Based on our previous findings, we obtain (see equation 95)

$$a_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) + (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (127)$$

□

3.15. The determination of the tensor $(b_{\mu\nu}) + (c_{\mu\nu})$

Theorem 15.

The unification of gravity and electromagnetism is given as

$$b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (128)$$

Proof by direct proof. It is

$$a_{\mu\nu} + b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} \quad (129)$$

or

$$b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} = R_{\mu\nu} - a_{\mu\nu} - d_{\mu\nu} \quad (130)$$

Based on our previous findings, we obtain (see equation 95)

$$b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{2}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (131)$$

□

The unification of gravity (general relativity) and electromagnetism (quantum electrodynamics) is one of the central goals of theoretical physics, often referred to as the grand unification or unification of fundamental forces. Several attempts and theoretical frameworks have been proposed to unify these two fundamental forces of nature. Equation 131 provides another approach to this issue. In the Kaluza-Klein theory, an important precursor to string theory which has been developed by Theodor Kaluza (see [Kaluza, 1921](#)) and Oskar Klein (see [Klein, 1926a,b](#)) in the 1920s, the space-time is described in higher dimensions (usually five dimensions), and the electromagnetic field arises as a geometric property of the extra dimensions. String theory itself is a highly ambitious and mathematically complex framework that attempts to unify all fundamental forces, including gravity and electromagnetism. According to the string theory, the fundamental building blocks of the universe are tiny, vibrating strings. Still, achieving a complete and experimentally verified unification of gravity and electromagnetism remains an open challenge in theoretical physics. However, unifying gravity and electromagnetism can have implications for our understanding of the early universe and cosmology and can provide cosmological solutions that can be explored to understand the evolution of the universe. Thus far, as already proofed, it is (see equation 64)

$$c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} g_{\mu\nu} \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) \quad (132)$$

and (see equation 10)

$$b_{\mu\nu} + c_{\mu\nu} + d_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{R}{2} g_{\mu\nu} \right) - (\Lambda \times g_{\mu\nu}) + \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{4} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta} \right) \right) \quad (133)$$

The consequences to consider if certain conditions, such as $a_{\mu\nu} = 0$, $b_{\mu\nu} = 0$, $c_{\mu\nu} = 0$, $d_{\mu\nu} = 0$, etc., are given have already been discussed elsewhere (see [Barukčić, 2016b](#)).

4. Discussion

The profound (philosophical) questions surrounding the nature of (theoretical) physics and its relationship with empirical experience was addressed even by Einstein himself. Einstein's successful unification of gravity with the geometry of space-time within the theory of General Relativity encouraged him to extend his approach to search for a definitive path to uncover the foundational truths of nature and to establish a unified basis for physics. Unfortunately, Einstein's ambitious unified field theory program which sought to unify gravity and electromagnetism, as well as potentially other forces, into a single set of equations that would describe the entire universe didn't yield success. Despite his dedication and numerous attempts, Einstein did not succeed in formulating a complete and satisfactory unified theory during his lifetime. While Einstein's unified field theory program did not achieve its ultimate goal, the same played a crucial role in advancing (theoretical) physics. Einstein's unified field theory program inspired subsequent generations of physicists to explore unification and seek deeper connections between fundamental forces. Even today, the unified field theory program is the search for a theoretical framework that aims to describe all fundamental forces of nature in a single, coherent mathematical framework while addressing questions related to dark matter, dark energy, and the fundamental nature of space-time. However, the goal to unify all the fundamental forces of nature under a single set of equations is still associated with problems. There is none geometric description of the electromagnetic field or of the stress-energy tensor of ordinary matter. Unifying gravity and electromagnetism, which have different mathematical structures and behaviors, present significant challenges as long as matter and the electromagnetic field is not geometrized simultaneously. Nonetheless, we have provided some evidence to the contrary and can summarise our current findings on the topic of unified field theory as follows (see table 8).

		Curvature		
		YES		NO
Momentum	YES	$a_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\left(\frac{4 \times 2 \times \pi \times G \times T}{c^4 \times D} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu}$	$b_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu}$	$\left(\frac{R}{D} g_{\mu\nu} \right) - \left(\frac{R}{2} g_{\mu\nu} \right) + (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu})$
	NO	$c_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \right) - \Lambda \right) g_{\mu\nu}$	$d_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\left(\frac{R}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{1}{\mu_0} \left(\left(\frac{g^{\mu\nu} F_{\mu\alpha} F_{\nu}^{\alpha}}{D} \right) - \left(\frac{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) g_{\mu\nu}$	$\left(\frac{R}{2} g_{\mu\nu} \right) - (\Lambda g_{\mu\nu})$
		$G_{\mu\nu} \equiv \left(\frac{R}{D} - \frac{R}{2} \right) g_{\mu\nu}$	$\frac{R}{2} g_{\mu\nu}$	$R_{\mu\nu} \equiv \frac{R}{D} g_{\mu\nu}$

Table 8. Einstein's field equations, the four basic fields of nature

However, even if driven by a deep desire to find a unified description of the fundamental forces of nature, without referring to the spatio-temporal dimension D, this endeavor seems to be difficult or even impossible to achieve. A successful Unified Field Theory should incorporate both quantum mechanics and general relativity by the same a single set of equations. This is particularly challenging because these two theories have different mathematical frameworks and scales of operation. Meanwhile, quantum gravity attempts to merge these two theories into a coherent framework.

5. Conclusion

‘The evidence is increasing that we are approaching more and more the unified field theory.’

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

Liebe Inge,
Ich werde dich immer
in meinem Herzen tragen.
Ruhe in Frieden.
Jever, 23.8.2023

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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